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A Timer triggered twice may explain Displaced Reflex Peaks in Serial Compound Conditioning but severely questions the Use of a Network Based Timer Mechanism.

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Abbreviations :

CF	Climbing fiber	ISI	Interstimulus interval
CMT	Cross-modal transfer	LTD/P	Long term depression/potential
CR	Conditioned response	MF	Mossy fiber
CS	Conditioned stimulus	NI	Nucleus Interpositus
	CSL Light-CS	NMR	Nictitating membrane response
	CST Tone-CS	NON	Nucleo-olivary neuron
	T=>L CST followed by CSL	NuC	Nuclear cell
EBR	Eyeblink reflex	PF	Parallel fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PuC	Purkinje cell
GrC	Granule cell	TM	Timing mechanism
GrL	Granular layer		ICTM Intracellular TM
HP	Hyperpolarization		NBTM Network based TM
HP-R	HP-rebound	US	Unconditioned stimulus
IO	Inferior olive		

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

ABSTRACT

Kehoe's 'serial compound' experiments demonstrate CR peaks leading or lagging the US, a phenomenon which the 'spectrum of microstimuli' hypotheses cannot explain.

'Serial compound' refers to a conditioning paradigm during which two different CSs are presented in succession (hence with different ISIs) BEFORE the US is administered.

The 'spectrum of microstimuli hypothesis' – in the cerebellar context - assumes that the CS onset signal triggers a timing mechanism [TM] that is based on interactions in the GrL network : a 'network based TM' [NBTM].

Classically it is believed that a consistent US induces LTD at the PF-PuC synapses of the GrCs which happen to be recurrently activated by the NBTM around US time, ultimately causing the PuCs to pause around US time, disinhibiting the NI to produce a CR.

It will be shown how a TM that is triggered twice (which in turn is an effect of 'cross-modal transfer' [CMT]) can lead to displaced CR peaks. The predicted displacements do not concur completely with those observed by Kehoe, but a tentative explanation for this discrepancy will be offered.

However, it will be argued that an NBTM which lends itself to be triggered twice, is inevitably also an NBTM which exhibits CMT in all testing situations – not only in Kehoe's experimental setup, and this argument, amongst others, severely questions the concept that the cerebellum engages an NBTM for NMR(-like) conditioning purposes.

An intracellular TM [ICTM] in the PuCs as demonstrated by Johansson et al. is a much better candidate to 'implement' this kind of conditioning and to explain Kehoe's observations, since it can escape CMT in other situations thanks to a (hypothesized) CS segregating mechanism in the nucleus interpositus.

'Displaced' CR peaks by themselves may also explain why 'Kamin blocking' fails when serial compound training follows full training with one of the CSs, while it is observed to occur when simultaneous compound training follows.

INTRODUCTION

Let's focus on Kehoe's article (2013) about timing and cue competition in the NMR.

In a first 'simultaneous compound' experiment a tone-CS [CST] and light-CS [CSL] are given simultaneously and the results show that the CRs on testing with CST only or CSL only are less strong than when both CST and CSL are combined, but the timings are always as expected i.e. clustered around the US.

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

"Training with the simultaneous compound reduced the likelihood of a conditioned response (CR) to the individual CSs ("mutual overshadowing") but left CR timing unaltered."

"These findings are consistent with previous findings in which timing was preserved despite cue competition effects."

In a second 'serial compound' experiment, the CSL is given 400ms after the CST [T=>L] (with US at 800ms). At testing time the resulting CR strengths concur with experiment 1, but - surprisingly - the timings deviate : when T=>L is presented the CR is clearly accelerated, when only CSL is presented the CR is clearly decelerated.

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

"In both cases, serial compound training altered CR timing. On CSA-CSB test trials, the CRs were accelerated; the CR peaks occurred after CSB onset but well before the time of US delivery. Conversely, CRs on CSB-trials were decelerated; the distribution of CR peaks was variable but centered well after the US. Timing on CSB-trials was at most only slightly accelerated."

"The acceleration in CR timing seen on CSA-CSB trials appeared to be a unique result of serial compound training and not of the simultaneous compound training."

The second experiment is also carried out after a pretraining session with CSL alone. Kehoe – in the subsequent serial compound training – not only observes that the expected 'Kamin blocking' fails, but also that CSL pretraining accentuates the T=>L CR acceleration.

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

"In Group BB, the peaks during CSA-CSB2 trials occurred another 100 msec earlier (M=577 msec) ."

Certainly, CR peaks occurring way before the US are totally at odds with the logic of US-triggered plasticity, which demands that the peaks should cluster around the US.

[2] (Medina et al. 2000)

"Conditioned responses are precisely timed; they begin before, and always peak at, the time when the air puff is expected."

The 'spectrum of microstimuli' hypotheses cannot explain these timing deviations.

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

"This type of model can explain the results of Experiment 1, in which the CR peaks were consistently aligned with the US across wide variations in response levels, especially the mutual overshadowing in Group TL. By the same token, the key results of Experiment 2 cannot be readily explained by these models."

METHODS

A demo program written in Visual Foxpro 9.0 has been used to provide for some 'visualization' of the argumentation.

THE NBTM

The 'spectrum of microstimuli hypothesis' assumes the GrL to implement an NBTM by interactions in the GrL network which generate a time-diversified firing sequence of GrCs when triggered by a CS onset signal coming in by the MFs.

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

"According to these models, there is a spectral timing process in which each CS is encoded by an array of asynchronous microstimuli that provide a distinctive pattern at each time point (Desmond and Moore 1988; Grossberg and Schmajuk 1989; Gluck et al. 1990; Buonomano and Mauk 1994; Machado 1997; Kirkpatrick and Church 1998; Buhusi and Schmajuk 1999; Vogel et al. 2003; Buhusi and Meck 2005; Ludvig et al. 2008, 2009; Lepora et al. 2010)."

When a consistent US induces LTD at the PF-PuC synapses which happen to be activated by GrCs around US time, it will ultimately cause the PuCs to pause around US time, disinhibiting the NI to produce a CR.

Medina and Mauk in their EBR simulation (2000) implemented an NBTM by relying on Golgi cells to obtain a 'reverberating' effect in the GrL.

[2] (Medina et al. 2000)

"The ability of simulated granule cells to fire at different times during the CS arises naturally as a consequence of the complex patterns of granule cell excitation and inhibition that result from dynamic interactions among mossy fibers, granule cells and Golgi cells."

The need for an NBTM arises from the ‘monotony’ of the trigger : it cannot be expected to generate time diversified GrC firing by itself.

[2] (Medina et al. 2000)

“Note the minimal temporal variation because mossy fibers are activated either throughout tone presentation or just at its onset.”

In vivo a comparable NBTM can be found in the electrosensory lateral line lobe [ELL] (a cerebellum-like structure in mormyrid fish), where unipolar brush cells are involved instead of Golgi cells (producing a ‘cascading’ effect), where a brisk electric organ corollary discharge is the trigger instead of a CS, and where it is used to filter out the electrosensory disturbance caused by the electric organ itself – a decorrelating procedure.

[3] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

“Weakly electric mormyrid fish emit brief EOD pulses for communication and active electrolocation. However, the fish’s own EOD also affects passive electroreceptors tuned to detect external fields.”

“Previous studies have shown that such interference, a ringing pattern of activation that may persist for as long as the interval between EODs, is cancelled out in medium ganglion cells through the generation of motor corollary discharge responses that are temporally-specific negative images of the sensory consequences of the EOD.”

In the ELL the NBTM provides timing diversity to ‘sculpt’ an output signal over a whole time lapse. Using the NBTM to ‘capture’ just one specific timing (as in NMR/EBR conditioning) feels like a waste of its purpose and abilities.

NBTMs of this type can be said to be ‘time-locked’ since they follow a network determined course once triggered. The pattern of time-diversified GrC firing that is produced will be different when another trigger signal enters the local network by another MF route or if a second signal intervenes during the reverberation/cascading devolution which is already ongoing, while it is adamant that ‘the end result’ i.e. which GrCs fire at US time, should be the same at training time and at testing time (a ‘reproducibility requirement’).

Consider that Kehoe uses $T \Rightarrow L$ for training but tests with CSL only and CST only.

Consider that Jirenhed observes that a CS must last throughout the ISI during (delay) training but that a brisk CS onset signal suffices when testing.

[4] (Jirenhed et al. 2011)

“It is worth noticing that the animals were trained with a delay paradigm in which the CS continues throughout the ISI. We are only claiming that a single pulse is all that is necessary to elicit a CR after it has already been learned. A sustained CS signal might still be necessary for learning.”

Delivering a different signal to an NBTM at training time and at testing time will pose a serious ‘reproducibility issue’.

Consider also that the EBR-simulation by Medina and Mauk (2000) demonstrates that the requirement that CR-onset is to advance the US by a relatively large timelapse complicates matters since prolonged GrC firing is necessary to force the advance, and the resulting coarse temporal coding calls for a remedy. LTP (which in itself can cause a runaway problem when not ‘capped’) is to be engaged to make the PuCs pause briskly in front of the US.

[2] (Medina et al. 2000)

“However, this same simulation revealed that during realistic tone-like inputs (which include mossy fibers that fire tonically throughout the entire tone) the geometry of cerebellar cortical connections caused many granule cells to become activated through large portions of the tone. This coarse temporal coding, in contrast to the sharp temporal specificity of granule cells proposed in topdown models, resulted in abnormally broad responses and thus failed to generate temporally specific learning.”

“Perhaps the most surprising result from these more complete simulations was that broad responses could be sharpened by incorporating evidence that in addition to LTD, $grc \rightarrow Pkj$ synapses can also undergo LTP when active without a climbing fiber input.”

The NBTM in the ELL is not confronted with the ‘advanced onset’ problem.

Sharp or coarse timing, the former arguments challenge the concept that an NBTM generates the timing in NMR-like conditioning, but Kehoe’s experiments may provide a ‘fatal’ argument :

Consider first a ‘segregated’ scenario : i.e. a CST enters the GrL in a region which is physically distant enough from the region where the CSL enters it, such that CST and CSL trigger ‘local’ NBTMs that do not involve the same GrCs.

We then expect that after training, compounded or not :

- the CST with an ISI of 800 ms will show a CR peak 800 ms after CST-onset when tested.
- the CSL with an ISI of 400 ms will show a CR peak 400 ms after CSL-onset when tested.
- presenting CSL 400 ms after CST will cause the PuCs in both regions to react simultaneously 800 ms after the CST.

With no mutual interference of the involved regions in the GrL the CR peak will stay close to US time : displaced peaks are not to be explained. (The convergence of PuC output onto the NI will affect peak amplitude though).

Now consider a non-segregated scenario : CST and CSL both enter in the same GrL region such as to have an effect on a shared GrC set (multimodal MF convergence onto GrCs allowing). Whatever the training protocol with CST and CSL (compounded or not, simultaneously or serially) : we may expect there to be always a subset of GrCs that reacts to CST as well as to CSL ('OR-gating') for every moment after both CSs have been delivered – the contrary would be utmost improbable.

A CR elicited by CST as well as by CSL means that there is cross-modal transfer [CMT] (it will become apparent by showing a 'double peaks' phenomenon when the CSs were trained with different ISIs). This phenomenon will allow to explain Kehoe's displaced peaks but by the same token it is a fatal problem for the NBTM concept : CMT will be lurking in whatever NMR-like conditioning protocol, while that is not observed in vivo since it occurs only in very special circumstances, Kehoe's 'compound' conditioning protocol being one of them.

The underlying reason for this is that the GrL has no means to 'undo' CMT, i.e. to segregate the shared GrC set into a CST-only and a CSL-only one. There is no signal to tell which GrCs are to 'get rid' of their specific multi-modal arrangement, and if they could then Kehoe's displaced peaks would become inexplicable again. It is the one or the other.

Clearly, in Kehoe's compound setup, the US makes the difference (the two CSs have to advance the US). However, CFs go straight to the PuCs, and bypass the GrL. The site where MFs and CFs really converge is in the deep nuclei, in casu the NI.

It led me to hypothesize that a CS segregation mechanism is to be sought in the NI, not in the GrL, and as a further consequence one has to adhere to the ICTM concept of Johansson [5] (Johansson et al. 2014), since ICTMs reside in PuCs, not in the GrL.

Johansson demonstrated that an mGluR7 based intracellular TM (an ICTM) in the PuCs works independently of any timing signal that might come in over the PFs, by using the technique of 'drowning' all PF traffic in a massive current injection, thereby obliterating any NBTM effect : a perplexing finding.

[6] Johansson et al. (2016)

"A recent study provides evidence for a radically new view of the mechanisms for motor timing in the cerebellum.

Contrary to the predictions of existing models, pairing a CS consisting of direct stimulation of the parallel fibers with a US consisting of direct climbing fiber stimulation led to a Purkinje cell CR that was adaptively timed.

That is, the cell reached maximum suppression <75 ms before the onset of the US regardless of CS-US interval.

This was an unexpected finding because with direct stimulation of parallel fibers, any temporal patterns of granule cell activity are presumably bypassed."

The hypothesis of a segregation mechanism in the NI is developed in [7] Beunis (2021b) . It builds on Johansson's ICTM on the condition that CFs and not PFs 'announce' the CS to the PuCs, and on the 'nucleo-olivary' bridge demonstrated by Ten Brinke et al. – which permits the CS to be transmitted by the CFs to the PuCs.

[8] Ten Brinke et al. (2015)

"The presence of the CS-complex spike means the CS-encoding signal has acquired the means to reach the olivary nucleus.

Insofar as the eyeblink paradigm used here contains an operant component in that the CR can reduce the aversive impact of the air puff US (Longley and Yeo, 2014), cerebral cortical involvement might possibly be involved. In any case, the strong Purkinje cell-wise link between the occurrence of CS-complex spikes and the magnitude of simple spike suppression suggests interdependent plasticity mechanisms underlying both phenomena. An interesting possibility is that loops within the olivocerebellar network could play a role.

The origin of the CS-complex spike could lie in the mossy fiber collaterals to the cerebellar nuclei that are newly formed over the course of conditioning (Boele et al., 2013), which could establish a straightforward bridge to cross for CS-encoding signals to directly hook up to the nucleo-olivary pathway (De Zeeuw et al., 1988) ."

The [7] Beunis (2021b) article in turn refers to [9] Beunis (2021a) in which the concepts of 'privileged partner connections' [PPCs] and 'nanoloops' are introduced.

A PPC refers to a heavily reinforced connection between PuC axon terminals and nuclear cells in the NI, 'privileged' because it only 'grows' between PuCs and NuCs which share a common CF (it might explain the 'connectivity asymmetry' mentioned in [10] Uusisaari (2011)). A 'nanoloop' is the olivo-cerebello-nucleo-olivary loop restricted to these PuC-NuC partners. The NI embraces a whole collection of nanoloops. Nanoloops allow for a functional refinement in a microzone.

[10] (Uusisaari et al. 2011)

"It is known that a single PN axon can form as many as 50 on some and as few as one synaptic terminal on other target neurons (Palkovits et al. 1977), suggesting that even though a CN cell could be contacted by a large number of individual presynaptic PNs, most of the synaptic terminals could be formed by axonal branches from just a few (3–4) presynaptic PNs with tens of presynaptic terminals each."

For the sake of the argument here, we can proceed by 'mentally' substituting the CST-only, CSL-only and CST+CSL GrC subsets with CST-only, CSL-only and CST+CSL nanoloop subsets (both get MF input, the latter via MF collaterals that sprout and contact NuCs), and by accepting that 'activated nanoloops' trigger the ICTMs which reside in 'their' PuCs as GrCs did with their PF synapses.

THE DOUBLE TRIGGERING PROCESS

In [7] [Beunis \(2021b\)](#) it is hypothesized that the NI harbours a mechanism that will segregate a CST+CSL nanolooop population into CST-only and CSL-only populations. It was noted however that this segregation process cannot occur in a compound experiment, due to both CSs advancing the US, and hence a tentative explanation of Kehoe's displaced CR peak observations can be given without having to elaborate on the segregation process itself.

Consider the 'serial compound' setup of Kehoe :

When testing for T=>L (after training for T=>L) we may expect

- a CR peak 800 ms after CST-onset contributed by the CST-only subset ('peak 1'),
 - a CR peak 400 ms after CSL-onset contributed by the CSL-only subset but occurring 800 ms after CST-onset since CSL-onset itself lags 400 ms after CST-onset ('peak 4'),
 - a CR peak 800 ms after CST-onset contributed by the CST+CSL subset ('peak 3'), and
 - a CR peak 400 ms after CST-onset contributed by the CST+CSL subset ('peak 2')
- since the 400 ms timers in it are triggered by CST before CSL gets the chance to do it.

Let's visualize it in fig. 1 :

Fig. 1 .

US at 800 ms (red vertical).
Tone CRs pink, light CRs cyan.

I assume here that 800 ms timer units in the CST+CSL subset are not disturbed any more in their 'countdown' when CSL occurs [4] [Jirenhed \(2011\)](#), and that 400 ms timer units in this same subset, triggered at CST onset, are refractory to being immediately retriggered at CSL onset.

(Note that these two requirements are impossible to guarantee in an NBTM).

I depict all peaks here with equal height (while it may depend on the respective set volumes), but the essential point here is the emergence of an early peak at 400 ms.

[4] ([Jirenhed et al. 2011](#))

We conclude that the time course of the Purkinje cell CR is determined by the initial part of the CS and is independent of the temporal pattern of parallel fiber activity during all but the very first few milliseconds.

The results suggest that the initial part of the CS signal triggers a mechanism for reducing the Purkinje cell firing with a specific, but adjustable, delay and duration, and that once this mechanism is activated, it runs its course relatively independent of further input.

An ICTM permits testing with a CS that differs in modulation from the CS used at training, while an NBTM doesn't.

After 250 iterations (simulating as much training trials) the CST+CSL PuCs will have generated two timer sets, one of which causes a HP 400 ms after CST onset (in Kehoe's timing), adding an additional 'early' CR peak well before the US.

...

When an 'early' peak (peak 2) is synchronously growing, it might explain the bimodality seen in the early phase of T=>L testing , since it may differ in which animals the early or the late peaks start eliciting NMRs first.

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

"In Group A-B, the peak distributions in Phase 1 initially showed some bimodality, but settled into a unimodal distribution centered 120 msec before US onset in Phase 2 (M=680 msec) ."

I expect 'population stochastics' to cause a fusion of peaks in the later phase : compare A=>B in left and right diagram of fig. 2 .

Fig. 2 [1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

The author used A=>B instead of T=>L because the experiment was 'counterbalanced', i.e. using as much L=>T) .

[11] Jirenhed (2017) demonstrated that - for a same CS delivered alternatively with two different ISIs - single PuCs are able to 'record' two different timings (but hardly more than two).

[11] (Jirenhed et al. 2017)

"We studied Purkinje cells in decerebrate ferrets that were conditioned using electrical stimulation of mossy fiber and climbing fiber afferents as CS and US, while alternating between short and long interstimulus intervals. We found that Purkinje cells can learn double pause responses, separated by an intermediate excitation, where each pause corresponds to one interstimulus interval. The results show that individual cells can not only learn to time a single response but that they also learn an accurately timed sequential response pattern."

In my view the same happens in Kehoe's serial compound experiments, but the two CR peaks in Jirenhed's case do not fuse (due to the large difference in ISI duration), while those in Kehoe's experiment do (with an even larger difference in ISI duration), the reason probably being that these peaks are growing simultaneously here.

[11] (Jirenhed et al. 2017)

"To promote learning of clearly separable response components, we wanted to use ISIs that were sufficiently different that separate pause responses would not merge into one. This meant the second ISI had to be relatively long compared with the first. However, conditioning with long ISIs requires more time (3, 13, 24), and the acute setup in these experiments provides only a limited window for studying learning effects. In this trade-off, we settled on a paradigm with a 300-ms difference between the two ISIs (150 and 450 ms) . This factor is a plausible cause of the observed long-duration pauses."

"We alternated between two ISIs so that the US was presented after either 150 or 450 ms after CS onset. On every tenth trial, the CS was presented alone to probe for learning effects. The choice of ISIs was determined by two considerations. If the difference between the two ISIs is too small, there is a risk, suggested by the behavioral literature (3, 15, 16, 23) and our own pilot experiments, that two PcCRs may merge together, rather than form two distinct pauses. Using very different ISIs, in contrast, means the second has to be quite long."

...

The net effect of all this will be, that - for T=>L testing - the merging of the four peaks will result in a peak that is 'accelerated' in reference to the US (since peak 2 leads on peaks 1, 3 and 4), and the amount of the advance will depend on the relative strengths of the peaks.

Fig. 3 gives an impression, the bicolored vertical indicating the position of the T=>L fused peak in reference to the component peaks (peak 2 'pulling it forward') and by overlaying Kehoe's diagram it can be seen to be in accordance with his observation : the A=>B peak in Kehoe's diagram coincides with the bicolored vertical where the 'fused peak' is expected to be.

Right on it or not, what really matters is that both precede the US : the peak is 'accelerated'.

Fig. 3
 overlaid with Kehoe's diagram
 [1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

T=>L test :
 the bicolored vertical and the
 A=>B peak both precede the US.

When testing for CSL alone, the CST-only subset produces no peak (no peak 1), and the populations triggered by CSL must be aligned, so peak 4 has to be advanced (and US time reference alike).

The same merging effect on peaks 2, 3 and 4 will now result in a decelerated peak, since peak 3 lags on 2 and 4 (pulling backwards) – see fig. 4 - (and compare again with the diagram).

The B (CSL) peak seems to lag much more in Kehoe's diagram.

Fig. 4
 overlaid with Kehoe's diagram
 [1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

CSL only test :
 the cyan vertical and the B-peak
 both lag behind the US but the
 B-peak lags much more.

Peak 3 appears at 1200 ms, i.e.
 800 ms after CSL onset, due to
 CST timers triggered by CSL.

Applying now the same logic on the testing with CST alone (merging peaks 1, 2, and 3 and having no peak 4) however, a peak is predicted that should even be more accelerated than the one for $T \Rightarrow L$, and such obvious acceleration is not to be seen in Kehoe's diagram – see fig. 5 - since the A (CST) peak there occurs after the US .

Fig. 5 overlaid with Kehoe's diagram [1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

CST only test : the pink vertical leads the US, but the A-peak lags behind it.

...

A possible explanation for this 'annoying deviation', can be found in Kehoe's 2009 article in which the same authors observe a relationship between the timing and the magnitude of the response.

[12] (Kehoe et al. 2009)

"Averaging across groups, the onset latencies decreased from 100% of the ISI for movements in the 0.11 mm-0.25 mm range down to 61% of the ISI for movements in the largest range ("4.01 mm) . The peak latencies declined from 179% to 116% of the ISI."

"The absolute timing of the NM movements differed across magnitudes. The smaller movements were highly variable. Their peaks, on average, tended to occur well after the time of US delivery. The larger movements, particularly for the 250-ms and 500-ms ISIs, were less variable in their timing, and their peaks were better aligned with the time of US delivery."

This effect might cause the peak latency of the weaker CST-only testing responses to 'retreat' in favour of the stronger $T \Rightarrow L$ testing responses, more or less annulling the expected acceleration in CST-only testing, and the same may hold for CSL-only testing, but now exaggerating the deceleration.

Indeed, in this study the authors used 'maximal closure' for the measure of maximal CR peak latency, discarding the use of a minimal criterion, and hence the timing-magnitude relationship may play a role in all situations where peaks are (or are still) weak.

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

"CR peak latency, as the index of timing, was the point of maximum NM closure on test trials relative to CS onset as measured on the nonreinforced test trials."

[13] (Garcia et al. 2003)

"Given the low level of noise in the rabbit eyelid preparations, there have been two strategies for measuring conditioned responding. One has been to use the maximal movement of the eyelid following CS onset. This measure, known as magnitude, entails all movements, even when only a very small movement (or no measurable movement) occurs. By using this measure, there is no need to adopt a criterion for denoting some movements as CRs while considering other movements to be too small to count as CRs."

[12] (Kehoe et al. 2009)

"Although scalar timing of the NM response might appear to be a settled matter, previous studies were restricted to NM movements that exceeded a minimum criterion, often 0."

Fig. 6 . [14] (Kehoe et al. 1993)

At great risk of misinterpretation I show a diagram in an earlier (and very difficult) article from Kehoe (1993) (focussing on the effect of different CSA=>CSB intervals) in which a CSA peak precedes the CSA=>CSB peak (the '250' dots) : cfr fig. 6.

(The '250' refers to the interval between CSA and CSB in the CSA=>CSB test).

In this study the 'minimal criterion' was used for measuring CR occurrence.

...

Fig. 7 . [1] (Kehoe et al. 2013)

In a variant of the second experiment the T=>L training is preceded by a training with CSL only, and Kehoe observes that this procedure leads to an accentuation of the T=>L CR acceleration, see Fig. 7 .

The upper diagram is the one which was overlaid in figs. 3, 4 and 5.

Compare the peaks in upper and lower diagram : all peaks are pulled forward in the lower diagram.

In accordance with the 'peak fusing hypothesis' as presented above, the accentuated advance might be explained by having stronger peaks 2 and 4 (CSL generated) of which peak 2 is 'early' - and maybe a partial blocking effect might have weakened peaks 1 and 3 (CST generated) too.

At the same time Kehoe is surprised to observe such an effect, since it should be expected that 'Kamin blocking' would prevent it to occur.

KAMIN BLOCKING

Kehoe observes that simultaneous compound training shows the expected 'blocking effect' when CST is added to an already well established CSL, but that blocking fails when serial compound training follows.

[15] (Rasmussen et al. 2014)

"A subject that has acquired CRs in response to one CS cannot acquire CRs to a second CS if it is presented together with the first one. For example, if a subject has learned to blink in response to a tone and one then adds a light, thus presenting the tone and the light simultaneously (still followed by the US), the subject will not learn to blink in response to the light. Put another way, the learned association to the first CS blocks association to the second CS. This phenomenon is known as Kamin blocking (Kamin, 1969) ."

[1] (Kehoe et al. 2013) (concerning serial compound training T=>L after pretraining with CSL only)

"The prior CSB_US training failed to block CR acquisition to CSA, which broadly agrees with the previous observations of very weak blocking of an added CSA (Kehoe et al. 1987)."

Two mechanisms are invoked to explain blocking :

A growing CR will cause the US to decline by having the eye protected in time, and there is also a ‘brake’ implemented by neurocircuitry since nucleo-olivary neurons [NONs] provide for a feedback that inhibits the IO and hence suppresses the US too.

[16] (Bengtsson et al. 2006)

"We reasoned that as neurones in the anterior interpositus nucleus learn to generate, say, a conditioned eyeblink, by increasing their firing in response to the conditioned stimulus, they will also provide an inhibitory signal to the inferior olive. As learning proceeds and nuclear output increases, the olive will gradually become more suppressed at the time of the unconditioned stimulus to the eye. Eventually, the climbing fibre signal to the cerebellum will be so weak that further learning ceases."

A negative feedback is never expected to annul an error altogether. In the case here a CR will extinguish a little bit at every trial when the US is inhibited too forcefully (as in ‘overexpectation’) and will be reinforced again a little bit when the US is inhibited too weakly. It will be kind of a ‘hovering’ around an equilibrium, certainly when random fluctuations also affect the US.

[15] (Rasmussen et al. 2014)

"A phenomenon related to Kamin blocking is overexpectation, which occurs when two CSs, each of which elicits a CR, are presented simultaneously, followed by the US . Initially, the simultaneous presentation results in a stronger CR; however, the strength of the CR will gradually decrease, even though the US is still presented (Kehoe and White, 2004) ."

"Learning to a second CS, when combined with a CS that is already producing CRs, may be blocked because the olivary inhibition generated by the CR suppresses the teaching signal (Kim et al., 1998) . In the light of the studies reviewed here, we suggest that this olivary suppression does not need to prevent the olive from firing entirely. To see the blocking effect, it might be sufficient that the nucleo-olivary inhibition changes the number of spikes in the olivary discharge."

Rasmussen suggests that US strength reverses its effect at a certain threshold.

[17] (Rasmussen et al. 2013)

"A single-pulse US caused extinction of the Purkinje cell CR. Increasing the number of pulses to two (500 Hz) did not result in reacquisition. However, three pulses (500 Hz) did result in reacquisition, and switching back to one pulse caused reextinction of the response. This suggests that the equilibrium level is close to two spikes."

Concerning Kamin blocking it means that it cannot be ‘absolute’, even when adding CST simultaneously with CSL : if training is maintained long enough blocking should ‘give way’, but it will be a slow process.

[16] (Bengtsson et al. 2006)

"It was shown by Kamin that, if learning has occurred to a particular conditioned stimulus, learning to a second conditioned stimulus, presented simultaneously, *will be very inefficient.*" (my italics)

Indeed, what counts for Kamin blocking is :

[15] (Rasmussen et al. 2014)

"... the olivary inhibition resulting from the Purkinje cell CRs should reach its maximum at about the same time that the US arrives at the inferior olive." (as eye protection should do too)

and as long as this requirement is fulfilled it will be strenuous to ‘overcome’ the blocking.

However, as soon as blocking hesitatingly ‘gives way’ under the ‘pressure’ of serial compounded training, an advanced peak will start to appear, which desynchronizes more and more with the US (eye protection and feedback inhibition now advancing the US), and this ‘runaway’ process should then ‘incapacitate’ the blocking with increasing ease.

DISCUSSION

Kehoe’s compound conditioning experiments are important in that they show that the appearance of CMT is a function of the temporal relationship of the CSs with the US. When both precede the US (‘compounded’), CMT is seen, if not compounded, CMT is at most a fleeting appearance in the early phase of training.

A tentative explanation of the underlying mechanism was given in [7] Beunis (2021b) :

[7] Beunis (2021b)

"When two different CSs are applied, the involved MF-NuC synapses are treated as 'being of one kind' if both CSs precede the US related HP-R - as they are being jointly LTP'd (the 'compound' situation of Kehoe - ISIs overlap). But if the ISIs do NOT overlap, CS1 synapses will be LTP'd while CS2 ones are LTD'd, and CS2 synapses will be LTP'd while CS1 ones are LTD'd, and the most frequently applied CS will win this game and subdue the other (in the nanoloops that have NuCs that connect to the two CS related MF modalities) ."

Unwittingly, Kehoe shows what the consequences of non-segregation are, and – interpreted in this light - his experiments strongly indicate that such a mechanism is at work, ensuring that CS1 ‘does not thread on the toes’ of CS2 and vice-

versa, by reorganizing connectivity in such a way that both CSs use neurocircuitry resources that do not interfere with each other, even when physically intermingled.

To implement it, it is first necessary to ‘discretize’ the available neurocircuitry in elementary units. The formation of ‘nanoloops’ [9] Beunis (2021a) during the juvenile multi-innervation phase of CFs onto PuCs means that OCNO-loop philosophy is not just applicable on the scope of a microzone, but ‘drills down’ to the scope of the small groups of NuCs and PuCs that share a common CF input.

When this is done, the segregation mechanism is able to reorganize MF connectivity onto NuCs, in such a way that different nanoloops get ‘allotted’ to different CSs.

As a consequence CMT is only observed when still in the multi-innervation phase, or - after that - in the early phase of CS training when segregation is still incomplete, and, of course, when serial compound training is applied, creating a situation in which segregation cannot take place.

A segregation mechanism is unfeasible in the GrL, not only because of the enormous GrC population engaged by an NBTM compared to the number of NuCs (NONs actually) of which the MF connectivity would have to be changed, but primarily because the US – on which the mechanism depends – is only directly available to NuCs and not to GrCs.

Without a segregation mechanism an NBTM cannot escape CMT unless the involved GrC populations for every different CS are physically at a distance in the GrL, and when they are the NBTM cannot allow for ‘exceptional’ situations and be used to explain the double peaks and displaced peaks phenomena.

In my opinion it is a compelling argument against invoking an NBTM to explain NMR-like conditioning, apart from other problems as how it is to be explained that a CR can be tested with a CS signal that is different in modulation from the one used at training time.

Consequently it is as compelling to take the ICTM demonstrated by Johansson seriously. Admittedly, an ICTM has also to explain how CR-onset is to advance the US, but I gather that to be just a question of evolutionary ‘delay tuning’ of the produced timer units (Johansson suggests that a restricted number of ‘types’ exists, each type ‘preset’ to a specific delay, the proportional mixture of activated timer types determining the actual delay).

[2] Johansson et al. (2014)

“At the onset of the conditional stimulus the ‘recorder’ proteins start changing in a predictable way. We assume four possible conformational states: ‘-’, A, B and C. Suppose that for the first 100 ms they are all in the ‘-’ state, between, say, 100-250 ms most are in the A state, between 200-350 ms most are in the B state and between 300-400 ms in the C state.”

“Assume further that the recorder proteins interact with the unconditional stimulus in different ways depending on when it arrives. Suppose that when they are still in the ‘-’ state there is no effect, but when they are in either the A, B or C states, different activation sites are available for the unconditional stimulus. Activating the recorder proteins in one of the states may then cause translation or activation of particular timer units. In this way the learning mechanism selects appropriate timer units (the effector components that generate a response at the right time).”

“Let us imagine the existence of what we might name “timer units” (receptor subunits, proteins, channels. . .) that would provide receptors (or molecular structures that are activated by them) with distinct temporal activation profiles. The learning process would then select, among a finite number of such units, a combination that matches the temporal interval. These timer units are the effector components that generate a response at the right time.”

However, all this is not a plea against the existence of NBTMs. As mentioned, a very efficient one is at work in the ELL of mormyrid fish (and comparable species), and it is not to be excluded that they are ‘at work’ in the cerebellum itself, especially in regions of the GrL where unipolar brush cells are prominent.

The GrL-PF infrastructure can also provide for timing diversity by using the variations in MF input itself (no ‘reverberating’ nor ‘cascading’ needed).

[18] Johansson et al. (2015)

“In other learning situations, where peripheral mechanisms can provide a richer temporal variation in the input to the granule cell layer, temporal coding in the parallel fiber input to Purkinje cells would be available. Under these conditions, synaptic weight changes such as LTD at parallel fiber synapses could play their part in establishing a temporal profile to learned responses.”

When such an input is derived from ‘bodily states’ (e.g. from proprioception) the NBTM can be called ‘state-locked’, and able to output reproducible timing diversity over longer periods.

[19] (Manto et al. 2012)

“An orderly succession of states may serve as “trigger points” during the production of a skilled movement, even though the overall rate of the movement may vary from one instantiation to the next. Models in which the cerebellum is viewed as a state estimator highlight how this structure imposes temporal regularities with relative rather than absolute timing.”

Is an NBTM that does not depend anymore on a timing diversity generator internal to the GrL still to be called an NBTM? In any case the GrL network is still to ‘manage’ the MF signals – preformatted as they may be – as to generate a GrC firing sequence that can meet requirements as reproducibility, uniqueness and sufficient timing resolution.

CONCLUSION

The displaced CR peaks in Kehoe's serial compound experiments can be explained by a CMT effect : the involvement of a population of elements reacting as well to CST as to CSL.

If these elements were to be GrCs (the NBTM concept) it would be GrCs that receive multimodal input from CST and CSL. With the US LTD'ing the related PF-PuC synapses, the involved PuCs should react to both CSs. It implies however the (untenable) supposition that the GrC firing sequence generated in the GrL would be the same when presenting CST=>CSL, CST only or CSL only.

In the 'ICTM concept' these elements would be PuCs in which the ICTM, generated a set of timer units tuned to the ISI of CST and another set tuned to the ISI of CSL. At testing time these two timer unit sets can be activated by CST as well as by CSL.

In both concepts a double-peaked component appears if the ISIs are sufficiently different, which – after fusion with CST-only and CSL-only components - results in an US leading CR peak when CST is involved, and in an US lagging peak if CST is omitted at testing time. Fusion probably is a function of ISI difference and training being compounded or not.

When CSL was pretrained and already well established, ensuing training with CST is confronted with Kamin blocking, but ensuing training with CST=>CSL overcomes it and results in CR peaks which are more advanced as when CSL was not pretrained.

It is hypothesized that Kamin blocking is not 'absolute' (it being a negative feedback phenomenon), and that - once displaced CR peaks get the chance to emerge - they cause the IO inhibition peak to drift away from the US peak, thereby gradually removing the requirement to have Kamin blocking.

Kehoe's measurements show CR peaks for CST-only and CSL-only which lag more than CMT predicts, but this might have been caused by his use of the 'maximal closure' CR measurement method instead of the 'minimal criterion' one.

...

The NBTM concept (and the 'spectrum of microstimuli' hypothesis for that matter) is severely criticized as being 'explanatory' for NMR-like conditioning.

Since an NBTM is supposed to produce a unique pattern of microstimuli for every input, how is it to explain that this input can be different at training time and at testing time, and yet still capable of evoking the CR ?

Fatal for the NBTM concept in conditioning is that when it allows for CMT, it cannot get rid of CMT, and CMT would have to appear in non-compounded experiments too.

It does not, as Kehoe's experiments demonstrate, and the mutual temporal relationship of the CSs with the US makes the difference. The US cannot 'implement' this difference in the GrL since it does not show up there (and it would also have to cause connectivity changes on an enormous scale). It turns the focus onto the NI as the place where connectivity changes to undo CMT can be realized 'under the rule of the US'.

The further consequences are explained in more detail in [7] Beunis (2021b) : the connectivity changes in the NI implement a segregation of 'nanoloops' and hence also a segregation of PuCs. With the NBTM ruled out as the TM, they have to contain an ICTM – an idea which might appear far-sought if it was not demonstrated by Johansson et al. .

For these ICTMs to comply with the segregation mechanism they have to get the CS 'announcement' via LTP'd synapses of MF collaterals onto NONs which then use the 'nucleo-olivary bridge' - as demonstrated by Ten Brinke et al. - to convey the CS onset signal (by way of the CFs which 'belong' to the involved nanoloops) to the PuCs.

Note : The CS-related complex spikes - which Ten Brinke takes as evidence that the CS is passed on to the IO - can only be seen when the experimental setup is 'naturalistic' (delivering a real CS). Massive direct stimulations of PFs or MFs can trigger ICTMs too, but these methods respectively bypass the 'NI-IO-bridge' or stop its formation prematurely (the CR emerging), and hence prevent the appearance of CS-related complex spikes (and prevent actual segregation of CSs too).

Kehoe's compound experiments compel to consider the ICTM, the segregation mechanism and the 'nanoloops' as the ingredients which explain the conditioning phenomena as they are observed for the NMR, the EBR and comparable reflexes. The NBTM – time-locked or 'state'-locked – is certainly not to be discarded as a prime candidate for other phenomena which require a 'temporal profile'. If the infrastructure for both TMs is there, they might as well cohabitate if not cooperate, as future research might reveal.

REFERENCES

1. Kehoe, E. J., Ludvig, E. A., & Sutton, R. S. (2013). Timing and cue competition in conditioning of the nictitating membrane response of the rabbit. *Learning & Memory*, 20, 97-102. <https://doi.org/10.1101/lm.028183.112>
2. Medina, J. F., & Mauk, M. D. (2000). Computer simulation of cerebellar information processing. *Nature Neuroscience*, 3, 1205-1211. <https://doi.org/10.1038/81486>
3. Kennedy, A., Wayne, G., Kaifosh, P., Alvina, K., Abbott, L. F., & Sawtell, N. B. (2014). A temporal basis for predicting the sensory consequences of motor commands in an electric fish. *Nature Neuroscience*, 17(3), 416-422. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nn.3650>
4. Jirenhed, D.-A., & Hesslow, G. (2011). Time course of classically conditioned Purkinje cell response is determined by initial part of conditioned stimulus. *The Journal of Neuroscience*, 31(25), 9070-9074. <https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1653-11.2011>
5. Johansson, F., & Hesslow, G. (2014). Theoretical considerations for understanding a Purkinje cell timing mechanism. *Communicative & Integrative Biology*, 7(6), e994376. <https://doi.org/10.4161/19420889.2014.994376>
6. Johansson, F., Hesslow, G., & Medina, J. F. (2016). Mechanisms for motor timing in the cerebellar cortex. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 8, 53-59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cobeha.2016.01.013>
7. Beunis, R. (2021b). An Eye Blink Reflex Model based on an Intracellular Timing Mechanism in Purkinje Cells and on a Conditioned Stimulus Segregation Mechanism in the Nucleus Interpositus might explain the Double Peaks Phenomenon. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16452.76168>
8. Ten Brinke, M. M., Boele, H.-J., Spanke, J. K., Potters, J.-W., Kornysheva, K., Wulff, P., Ijpelaar, A. C. H. G., Koekkoek, S. K. E., & De Zeeuw, C. I. (2015). Evolving models of Pavlovian conditioning - cerebellar cortical dynamics in awake behaving mice. *Cell Reports*, 13, 1977-1988. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2015.10.057>
9. Beunis, R. (2021a). Olivo-Cerebello-Nucleo-Olivary Loops Connectivity might be refined during the juvenile multi-innervation Phase of Climbing Fibers onto Purkinje Cells. *ResearchGate*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19459.22563>
10. Uusisaari, M., & De Schutter, E. (2011). The mysterious microcircuitry of the cerebellar nuclei (Symposium Review). *Journal of Physiology*, 589(14), 3441-3457. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3167109/pdf/tjp0589-3441.pdf>
11. Jirenhed, D.-A., Rasmussen, A., Johansson, F., & Hesslow, G. (2017). Learned response sequences in cerebellar Purkinje cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 114(23), 6127-6132. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1621132114>
12. Kehoe, E. J., Olsen, K. N., Ludvig, E. A., & Sutton, R. S. (2009). Scalar timing varies with response magnitude in classical conditioning of the nictitating membrane response of the rabbit. *Behavioral Neuroscience*, 123(1), 212-217. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0014122>
13. Garcia, K. S., Mauk, M. D., Weidemann, G., & Kehoe, E. J. (2003). Covariation of alternative measures of responding in rabbit (*Oryctolagus cuniculus*) eyeblink conditioning during acquisition training and tone generalization. *Behavioral Neuroscience*, 117(2), 292-303. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0735-7044.117.2.292>
14. Kehoe, E. J., Horne, P. S., Macrae, M., & Horne, A. J. (1993). Real-time processing of serial stimuli in classical conditioning of the rabbit's nictitating membrane response. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Animal Behavior Processes*, 19(3), 265-283. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0097-7403.19.3.265>

15. Rasmussen, A., & Hesslow, G. (2014).
Feedback control of learning by the cerebello-olivary pathway.
Progress in Brain Research, 210, 75–92.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63356-9.00005-4>
16. Bengtsson, F., & Hesslow, G. (2006).
Cerebellar control of the inferior olive.
The Cerebellum, 5, 7–14.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14734220500462757>
17. Rasmussen, A., Jirenhed, D.-A., Zucca, R., Johansson, F., Svensson, P., & Hesslow, G. (2013).
Number of spikes in climbing fibers determines the direction of cerebellar learning.
The Journal of Neuroscience, 33(33), 13436–13440.
<https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.1527-13.2013>
18. Johansson, F., Carlsson, H. A. E., Rasmussen, A., Yeo, C. H., & Hesslow, G. (2015).
Activation of a temporal memory in Purkinje cells by the mGluR7 receptor.
Cell Reports, 13, 1741–1746.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.celrep.2015.10.047>
19. Manto, M., et al. (2012).
Consensus paper - roles of the cerebellum in motor control—the diversity of ideas on cerebellar involvement in movement.
Cerebellum, 11, 457–487.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12311-011-0331-9>